

Plate 1. Microscopic Characteristics of Some Wild and Domestic Species

1.1 Snow Leopard

Cuticle

Medulla

1.2 Blue Sheep

Cuticle

Medulla

Cross- section

1.3 Musk Deer

Cuticle

Medulla

Cross- section

1.4 Pika

Medulla

Cuticle

1.5 Yak

Cuticle

1.6 Common Leopard

Cuticle

1.7 Red Fox

Cuticle

1.8 Marmot

Cuticle

1.9 Cow

Cuticle

1.10 Goat

Cuticle